

Isolated pathogens, antimicrobial resistance pattern and clinical outcome of patients admitted to Intensive care unit of Tikur Anbessa Specialized Hospital from May 2023 to October 2023: A cross-sectional study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a global public health threat associated with clinical setbacks. We now encounter patients, particularly those admitted to intensive care units (ICU), harboring difficult to treat pathogens but there are major gaps in routine surveillance, antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) and reporting. The effect of AMR on patient outcome has also been inconsistent. The objective of the study was to identify commonly isolated pathogens, their antimicrobial resistance pattern and clinical outcome of patients admitted to the ICU of Tikur Anbessa Specialized Hospital (TASH).

Methods: An institution based 6 months retrospective cross sectional study conducted in the ICU of TASH on 216 patients. Simple random sampling was used as a sampling method. Data regarding sociodemographic and clinical characteristics, AST and outcome of patients was collected from the health management information system (HMIS). Data quality and completeness were assured by the principal investigator with each collected data by developing data entry forms. Statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 27 was used for data analysis. Categorical data was described in percentages and mean. Bivariate and multivariate logistic regression was used to assess the association between AMR and intra ICU mortality. P value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: All infections were mono microbial and bloodstream infection was the commonest. 89.4% of infections were due to gram negative bacteria. Of the gram negatives the most commonly isolated pathogen was *Acinetobacter baumannii* (31.5%) with carbapenem resistance *acinetobacter baumannii* (CRAB) infection being predominant. Multidrug resistance (MDR) was seen in 80.1% of the isolates. Intra ICU mortality was determined to have a significant association with bloodstream infection (AOR 2.89 95% CI 1.11, 3.94), septic shock (AOR 5.34 95% CI 2.32, 12.25), CRAB infection (AOR 2.22 95%CI 1.11, 4.43) and surgical intervention (AOR 0.46 95%CI 0.24, 0.88).

Conclusions: Gram negative bacteria are the commonest isolated pathogens in the ICU of TASH with most exhibiting high degree of resistance against the majority of antimicrobials. Blood stream infection, septic shock, medical admissions and CRAB infection were determined to be predictors of intra ICU mortality.

Key words: Antimicrobial resistance; Intensive care units; Mortality

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